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A study on different types of anxiety levels and self-confidence in snow and ice winter sports athletes

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to analyze the selected psychological parameters among winter sports athletes. Those subjects were selected who have played at least All India Inter- University in their relevant sport. The age of the subjects ranged from 20 to 25 year old and a total of sixty subjects (N=60) were selected. The selected subjects were divided into two groups, skiing (n=30) and ice stock (n=30) depending upon their winter sports game. For the purpose of the study Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 (CSAI-2), a sport-specific state anxiety scale developed by Martens, Vealey, and Burton (1990) was administered on the selected subjects. Descriptive and independent t test was employed. The study resulted that there was a significant different in cognitive state anxiety and self-confidence among skiing and ice stock players while there was no significant difference in and somatic state anxiety among skiing and ice stock players. The study resulted that cognitive state anxiety and self-confidence is significantly higher in skiing players than ice stock players.

Keywords: Competitive state anxiety inventory, 2 (CSAI-2), cognitive anxiety and somatic anxiety, self-confidence

Introduction

Great athletes require not only a combination of exceptional skills, natural talent, and peak physical condition, but also a supportive environment, willpower, and mental toughness (Holland *et al.*, 2010) [3]. Psychological traits are significant factors that influence athletic performance (Smith & Christensen, 1995) [13]. Sports performance and success in sport may be influenced by athletic coping mechanisms, anxiety, and stress, according to sports psychology research (Mahoney *et al.*, 1989) [9].

Anxiety is a well-studied topic in the field of sports psychology because understanding how anxiety affects athletes and how they can manage it effectively is a critical area of study (Jarvis, 2006) [6]. According to the multidimensional theory of anxiety (Martens *et al.*, 1990) [10], three dimensions of anxiety can be distinguished. The psychological and mental components of anxiety are referred to as cognitive anxiety. Worry, fear, and pessimistic thinking are some of the cognitive or thought-related aspects of anxiety. When someone has cognitive anxiety, their thoughts could race, they might imagine bad things happening, and they might find it difficult to focus. This aspect of anxiety is mostly focused on ideas and mental processes related to anxiety-provoking circumstances. Somatic anxiety, on the other hand, is associated with physical symptoms and physiological reactions that arise as a result of stress or anxiety (Lane *et al.*, 1999) [7].

Alpine skiing is one of the most popular winter sports with millions of people participating world-wide Contemporary research literature is mainly related to investigation of physical and physiological characteristics of elite alpine skiers, while research in the field of psychology is scarce, especially in case of recreational alpine skiing (Neumayr *et al.*, 2003). Competitors slide ice stocks over an ice surface, aiming for a target, or to cover the longest distance. Ice stocks have a gliding surface, to which a stick (ca 30 cm) is attached (International Olympic Committee, 2025) [5]. Ice stock sport, like many competitive activities, can be a source of both enjoyment and anxiety. While physical activity, including ice stock, can help reduce stress and anxiety, the competitive nature of the sport can also trigger anxiety in some individuals (Indian Ice stock Sports Association, 2025) [4].

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Methodology

This study involved sixty winter sports players. The subjects were selected from All India Inter university (AIU) winter games played at Gulmarg 2025. The age of the subjects ranged from 20 to 25 year old and a total of sixty subjects (N=60) were selected. The selected subjects were divided into two groups depending upon the game they represent their university at AIU winter games 2025. The selected subjects were divided into two groups, skiing (n=30) and ice stock (n=30) depending upon their winter sports game. A sport-

specific state anxiety measure created by Martens, Vealey, and Burton (1990) [10], the Competitive State Anxiety Inventory-2 (CSAI-2), was used for this study. Participants were asked to rate the severity of each individual symptom on the response scale; each sub-scale had a score between 9 and 36. The statistical analysis for the data collected was used by employing descriptive statistics and independent 't' test.

Result and Analysis

Table 1: Group Statistics and Independent t test

		Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. 2- tailed)
Cognitive anxiety	State	Skiing	30	23.30	2.52	0.46	2.21	58	0.031
		Ice Stock	30	22.10	1.56	0.28			
Somatic Anxiety	State	Skiing	30	21.86	2.54	0.46	1.11	58	0.717
		Ice Stock	30	21.80	2.36	0.43			
Self Confidence		Skiing	30	21.63	1.09	0.21	3.97	58	0.001
		Ice Stock	30	20.26	1.52	0.27			

The results indicate that there was significant difference in cognitive state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players, $t(58) = 2.21$, $P = 0.031$, which is less than 0.05. That is the average score of skiing players ($M=23.30$, $SD=2.52$) was statistically different from that of ice stock players ($M=22.10$, $SD=1.56$). Thus, it could be concluded that there was a significant difference in cognitive state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players.

The results indicate that there was no significant difference in somatic state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players, $t(58) = 1.11$, $P = 0.717$, which is greater than 0.05. That is the average score of skiing players ($M=21.86$, $SD=2.54$) was not

statistically different from that of ice stock players ($M=21.80$, $SD=2.36$). Thus, it could be concluded that there was a no significant difference in somatic state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players.

The results indicate that there was significant difference in self-confidence between skiing and ice stock players, $t(58) = 3.97$, $P = 0.001$, which is less than 0.05. That is the average score of skiing players ($M=21.63$, $SD=1.09$) was statistically different from that of ice stock players ($M=20.26$, $SD=1.52$). Thus, it could be concluded that there was a significant difference in self-confidence between skiing and ice stock players.

Fig 1: Graphical representation of mean values of selected variables among skiing and ice stock players

Discussion

There was a significant difference in cognitive state anxiety and self-confidence between skiing and ice stock players while there was no significant difference in somatic state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players. The physiological "fight or flight" response that the body experiences when it detects a threat or danger is reflected in somatic anxiety. Self-confidence, often known as self-efficacy, is the third element of Multidimensional Theory of Anxiety (Martens *et al.*, 1990) [10]. It deals with a person's confidence in their own capacity to carry out a specific activity or deal with a specific circumstance. Low self-confidence implies uncertainty and insecurity, whereas high

self-confidence indicates strong belief in one's talent. How people approach and react to events that cause anxiety is greatly influenced by their levels of self-confidence. When compared to people who have less self-confidence, persons with higher self-confidence may feel more capable of handling pressure and may have lower levels of anxiety (Vealey, 2002) [14]. In conclusion, the multidimensional theory of anxiety acknowledges that it is a multidimensional and complex experience that includes cognitive, physical, and self-confidence components. Individuals can benefit from an understanding of these qualities. The relationship between motivation regulations and anxiety has been widely researched using both variable and person-centred

approaches.

The relationship between quality of life, coach behaviour and competitive anxiety in young elite athletes competing at the first Winter Youth Olympic Games should be considered in long-term programmes for reducing competitive stress (Ledochowski *et al.*, 2012) [8]. Psychological factors and gender differences need to be considered during learning phases of alpine skiing. There is a positive association between self-efficiency and performance of male ski beginners, and negative association between fear and achieved results in basic alpine ski school in case of female ski beginners (Cigrovski *et al.*, 2018) [1]. Coaches should work with players to enhance their concentration and mental preparation skills. This can be done through specific training and drills, which may help players perform better under pressure (Gelei, 2022) [2].

Conclusion

Following conclusions are drawn

1. There was a significant difference in cognitive state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players. Thus it is concluded that skiing players have significantly higher cognitive state anxiety than ice stock players.
2. There was a no significant difference in somatic state anxiety between skiing and ice stock players.
3. There was a significant difference in self-confidence between skiing and ice stock players. Thus it is concluded that skiing players have significantly higher self-confidence than ice stock players.

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